

A Pilot Study Of Game Addiction And Its Connecti On With Emotional Disorders In Saudi Adolescents

Fahad Saeid Alanazi

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: November 12, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: June 13, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Game addiction, Depression, Anxiety, Hostility, Introduction</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6638996</p>	<p><i>Research indicates that Few studies have studied a link between game addiction and emotional disorders within Saudi adolescents, and no studies, to date, have published data on this correlation between both of which. This study aimed to examine the association between game addiction and the emotional disorders of depression, anxiety, and hostility in a sample of high school students from Tabuk region of Saudi Arabia.</i></p> <p>Methods</p> <p><i>The pilot study was conducted in early of 2021 among 130 students Students who returned signed consent forms and that included validated scale on addiction to video games, The Symptom Checklist-90-Revised (depression, anxiety, and aggression) selected subscales.</i></p> <p>Results</p> <p><i>Video game addiction scale was valid and reliable, also strongly associated with depression, anxiety, and hostility subscales. The results of Game addiction scale items were strongly used as predictors of depression, anxiety, and aggression.</i></p> <p>Conclusions</p> <p><i>The high and strong correlations between Game addiction scale and emotional disorders of depression , anxiety and hostility were found. These findings have suggested that more research should be carried out in the future to investigate the role of emotion regulation as a predictor of video game addiction..</i></p>

Introduction

Game addiction is currently one of the most predominant and significant aspects of psychosocial phenomena (Lemmens, Valkenburg and Peter, 2008; Young, 2009). The concept of game addiction was developed through ongoing research, and can be defined as problematic and abnormal behaviours caused by a person spending long hours in front of electronic devices. It is considered to be a type of compulsion that is known as behavioural addiction (Griffiths, 2000; Kasiri et al., 2011; Kardefelt-Winther et al., 2017; Baysa et al., 2018). For example, it can cause problems in a person's relationships with or attitudes towards friends, family members, physical appearance, and disability (Hussain and Griffiths, 2009). Recently considered as a mental disorder by common systems of the American Psychiatric Association (APA: 2013) and the World Health Organization (2020), it affects around 8.5%, 14% and 15% in the US, the UK and Europe respectively (Lopez-Fernandez, 2014); in addition, around 5% of a sample of 2,675 school students in Saudi Arabia were found to be addicted to gaming (Rajab et al., 2020).

There is a belief that psychosocial risk factors predispose the individual to developing mental and behavioural symptoms related to game addiction (Caplan, 2007, Davis, 2001). Lemmens, Valkenburg, and Peter (2010) carried out a study entitled "Psychosocial causes and consequences of pathological gaming". As a consequence, many studies have also shown that gaming is associated with a cluster of various problems that significantly affect a person's life (Griffiths, Kuss, and King, 2012). In a study carried out by Mintzon and others, which dealt with addiction to video games and the symptoms of some disorders, it was concluded that there is a correlation between addiction to video games and an increase in symptoms of stress, anxiety, and depression (Mentzoni et al., 2011). In addition, within Saudi adolescents, stress is found to be associated with game addiction by Saquib et al. (2017).

These are psychological risks, which include factors such as poor impulse control, as well as poor life satisfaction, low self-esteem, loneliness, social anxiety, depression, and aggression (Wang et al., 2019; Kim and Davis, 2009; Liu and Peng, 2009; Stetina et al., 2011). The common emotional disorders found to be related to game addiction are social anxiety and depression (Wei, Chen, Huang, and Bai, 2012; Wenzel, Bakken,

Johansson, Gotestam, and Qren,2009). According to Rujataronjai, and Varma "the higher the level of video game addiction, the higher the level of depression, anxiety, and stress" (2017.p151).

Some researchers have warned that over use of video games could lead to an increase in low levels of self-control, resulting in aggressive behaviour (Anderson, 2004; Anderson and Dill, 2000; Anderson and Ford, 1986; Funk and Buchman,2006; Anderson et al., 2010).

Addiction to use of the internet, which is available to everyone, is also wide spread, and can play a fundamental and significant role in the incidence of disorders such as depression (Young and Rogers, 1998). Notable occurrences of depression may also be associated with video games (Bruborgr, Mentzoni and Froyland,2014): previous studies have shown that the amount of time an individual devotes to playing electronic games is associated with higher levels of depression (Lemona et al.,2011).

Two recent studies conducted by Brand and others, as well as Ahmed and others, found there to be a link between addiction to internet and games and anxiety disorders (Brandetal.,2014; Ahmad et al.,2014).

In recent times there has only been one study carried out by Saudi researchers into gaming addiction and perceived stress among Saudi adolescents (Rajab et al.,2020); as previously noted (Lemmens, Valkenburg and Peter, 2009), the Game Addiction Scale (GAS) was used with no mention of the translated Arabic version and its validity or reliability. Several studies in Arab Gulf countries have examined different areas of research related to video games (Saqib et al.,2017); however, none of these studies tackled the emotional disorders (for example depression, anxiety, and aggression) potentially associated with game addiction. There has been little investigation of the connection between game addiction and mental disorders in Saudi Arabia. The purpose of this pilot study is to examine the association between emotional disorders and game addiction in a non-clinical sample of adolescent Saudi students. In order to investigate this association, the GAS aimed to translate from the English language into Arabic using translation and back translation. In addition, we proposed the following hypotheses:

- I- The GAS will have good psychometric properties of the translated GAS (Arabic original).
- II- The Symptom Checklist -90- Revised (depression, anxiety, and hostility) subscales will have a significant connection with the GAS.
- III- The GAS's elements will be used as predictors of depression, anxiety, and hostility.

Methods

Sample

Participants were recruited and information was collected from male high school students between the ages of 15 and 18 years (i.e.,across the three year groups); the sample included 260 adolescents from the city of Tabuk, who were chosen at random.

Game Addiction Scale

An English version of the GAS was initially compiled and specifically developed by Lemmens and others (Lemmens, Valkenburg, and Peter, 2009). To evaluate gaming usage among adolescents, the scale was translated from English into French and German (Khazaal et al., 2016). Participants were instructed to respond clearly to the scale's elements by answering in relation to their own game use.

According to the hypothesis (Lemmens et al., 2009), those who scored 'sometimes' or more on the seven statements where the items were defined as games (the games are satisfactory), and those who scored 'sometimes' or more for at least half of the items (four to six of the seven elements) were defined as multiplayer gamers (hyper-gamers). This seven-phase scale scored a Cronbach Alpha high reliability from 0.88 to 0.87 in the original study. A Cronbach's Alpha of .865 was found in the study in question.

Symptom Checklist-90-Revised

This was prepared by Lipman, Covi and Derogatis (1976), and was translated by Al-Buhairi (2005) from his original language into Arabic. The list consists of 90 words in the form of a self-report on psychological and mental symptoms, and was designed to reflect the multiple types of psychological and medical symptoms from which he suffers; these include physical symptoms, along with those of obsessive-compulsive disorder; inability to cope; sensitivity; depression; hostility; anxiety; fear; psychosis; and psychotic paranoia. For this study, three subscales have been chosen: depression, hostility, and anxiety. Cronbach's Alpha of depression subscale .879; anxiety subscale .819; and hostility .70 were found.

Ethical approval

The current research was approved by University of Tabuk Research Ethics Committee (No: 177), and all the participants and their guardians when applicable signed a written informed consent according to the Declaration of Helsinki.

Sample collection procedures

Data was collected over a period of four months. Initial contact was made with school principals in Tabuk secondary schools, to obtain permission to collect samples from their establishments. All resultant information from the study was presented to the principals. Once permission was granted, the researcher attended several sessions to provide information about the study. The researcher emphasized that participation in the study would be completely voluntary. Study questionnaires would be placed on the front table in classes, as well as a pack containing information sheets and consent forms for potential participants. The study packages contained two envelopes for return: one for completed consent forms, and one for completed questionnaires. This was to ensure that the responses would be as anonymous as possible. The papers were placed in an area that students could access when leaving classes. This aspect was mentioned in the accompanying information sheet, and the participants were given the opportunity to complete the questionnaires independently or arrange to speak with the researcher and complete the measures in his presence. Participants were asked to return the scales and consent forms (in the separate envelopes) to the boxes placed in the school manager office. The questionnaires and consent forms were given unique identification numbers, to ensure that any participants who wished to withdraw their data during the study would easily be able to do so.

Statistical analysis

SPSS 19.0 and AMOS 19.0 (for confirmatory factor analysis) were used in this study.

The first step was to verify the validity and reliability of the GAS with SPSS calculation, along with finding the Cohen Kappa coefficient to calculate the extent of the arbitrators' agreement. Calculation of reliability was via two methods: the first Cronbach's Alpha method, with the second being half-segmentation through Gottman and Spearman Brown's coefficient. Validity was determined by calculating the internal consistency of the scale through checking the correlation of the statement with its axis.

The second step was factor analysis validity calculation by confirmatory factor analysis method through the AMOS program.

The third step was to quantify the connection between gaming addiction and emotional disorders.

The fourth step was to carry out a multiple linear regression analysis of several equations by using the Stepwise method for depression, anxiety and hostility as dependent variables, and understanding which expressions of the GAS have the ability to predict the occurrence of disorders. The Stepwise method was used because it is not utilized in any other extant studies, and it was considered that the method would enrich the theoretical side of this research.

Power calculation

According to De Vellis, 'for a 20-item factor analysis, 100 subjects would probably be too few, but for a 90-item factor analysis, 400 might be adequate'. (De Vellis, 2012, p.157). There were 260 male participants in this examination of the 7-Game Addiction Scale, so around 37 subjects for each element.

Translation process

The developer of the GAS was contacted, and the researcher was given permission to carry out the translation and use the tool in this study. The GAS was subjected to a translation and back translation from English into Arabic and then back into English again by adopting the following method (Sinaiko and Brislin, 1973; Tamanin et al., 2002): the translation was performed by two people, each fluent in both English and Arabic as well as holding a doctorate in psychology. The back translation was from Arabic into English again, by two independent translators each holding a doctorate in psychology. The end result was then assessed by three arbitrators from the field of psychology.

Result

As previously mentioned, the main aim of this study was to examine the association between games addiction and the emotional disorders of depression, anxiety, and hostility. 260 subjects randomly took part, all subjects answered all of the items.

Analyses of Game Addiction Scale Properties

A secondary goal of the study was to examine some of the properties of the translated GAS (Arabic version) in a non-adolescent clinical sample.

The Kappa values index was tested, and the results show that Kappa values were all 1.000. Therefore, the levels of agreement by the experts for the method were high and significant; the analysis of inter-evaluator agreement demonstrates that there was a high degree of consistency between assessors at these stages of the translation process. (The statistics are based on the criteria developed by Landis and Koch, 1977.)

In addition, Table 1 shows that the reliability analyses of GAS showed that it had good Cronbach Alpha values, .856. Furthermore, the Spearman-Brown coefficient value for the treatment of other subscales was 0.833 (i.e., equal length), while the Guttman split-half coefficient value is 0.826. The two coefficients were thus significantly high, and supported the Cronbach Alpha result. In addition, corrected item total correlation for all items range between 0.574 and 0.708 >.350. Confirmatory factor analyses were then carried out using the AMOS 19.0 program to see if the current data corresponded (Lemmens et al., 2009). A maximum likelihood estimator was employed to compare structure coefficients between latent variables. Data from all 260 participants was entered into this analysis. In addition, indications of compatibility were as follows: the root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA) was 0.075 >.08 (Browne and Cudeck 1993). Furthermore, the comparative fit index CFI and the GFI obtained were 0.928 and 0.923 respectively, with both being > 0.9 (Hu et al., 1999; Chinomona, 2011). Factor loadings generally indicate a significant cross-loading of items across the factor. All items demonstrated very good factor loadings in relation to the single factor loading, and ranged between 0.698 and 0.771.

Table 1

7-Item	A	CITC	Factor loading		
Did you think about playing a game throughout the entire day?	.848	.613		.673	
Did you play for longer than you intended?	.849	.607		.643	
Did you play games to forget about real life?	.835	.705		.771	
Were you unable to reduce your gametime?	.865	.549		.598	
Have you felt bad when you were unable to play?	.836	.708		.766	
Did you have arguments with others (e.g., family, friends) about your time spent on games?	.836	.706		.771	
Have you neglected other important activities (e.g., school, work, sports) to play games?	.835	.574		.615	
Total Cronbach's Alpha	.865				
Spearman-Brown Coefficient Equal Length	.833				
Guttman Split-Half Coefficient	.826				
NOTE: A=Cronbach's Alpha if Item deleted, CITC=Corrected Item Total Correlation>.350					

The results of the relationship between psychological disorders and addiction of adolescents to game addiction

Table 2 includes Pearson correlation analysis results that are among research variables: the correlation between game addiction and depression, anxiety, and hostility subscales tested.

Table 2

		Depression	Anxiety	Hostility
Game addiction		0.755**	0.771**	0.658**
	**Correlation is significant at the 0.01			

Based on the findings obtained throughout analysis, a significant link can be observed between game addiction and all anxiety, depression, and hostility subscales, respectively. A correlation between game addiction and anxiety was found ($r = 0.771, p > .01$). In addition, the second correlation between game addiction and depression was also high ($r = 0.755, p > .01$). The connection between game addiction and hostility was significant ($r = 0.658, p > 0.01$).

Prediction of Depression Scores

Table 3 shows that significant contributions are made from the mood modification, conflict, and problems subscales in the prediction of depression subscale scores for all participants.

Table3

	Variable	Stand.Beta	Sig.T
Mood Modification	Did you play games to forget about real life?	.626	0.000
Conflict	Did you have arguments with others (e.g., family, friends) about your time spent on games?	.228	0.002
Problems	Have you neglected other important activities (e.g., school, work, sports) to play games?	.128	0.044
	MultiR2=0.826,R=0.682		
	DS=Depression subscale.GAS=Gameaddictionscale		

Prediction of Anxiety Scores

Table4 shows that significant contributions are made from the moodmodification ,withdrawal, and salience subscales in the prediction of anxiety subscales cores for all participants.

Table4

	Variable	Stand.Beta	Sig.T
Mood Modification	Did you play games to forget about real life?	.444	0.000
Withdrawal	Have you felt bad when you were unable to play?	.333	0.000
Salience	Did you think about playing a game throughout the entire day?	.199	0.000
	MultiR2=0.822,R=0.675		
	AS=Anxiety subscale. GAS= Game addiction scale		

Prediction of Hostility Scores

Table5 shows that significant contributions are made from the mood modification, tolerance, and conflict subscales in the prediction of hostility subscale scores for all participants.

Table5

	Variable	Stand.Beta	Sig.T
Mood Modification	Did you play games to forget about real life?	.503	0.000
Tolerance	Did you spend increasing amounts of time on games?	.186	0.018
Conflict	Did you have arguments with others (e.g., family, friends) about your time spent on games?	.163	0.024
	MultiR2=0.731, R=0.534		
	HS=Hostility subscale. GAS=Game addiction scale		

Discussion

As GAS matching with the Internet gaming disorder presented in new version of DSM-5 (Petry, Rehabein, and Gentile et al., 2014). One of the aims of this study was to provide a reliable and sound scale to measure game addiction within the Saudi sample. The psychometric characteristics of the 7-item GAS among the Saudi adolescents' sample was tested by checking the internal consistency. The Cronbach Alpha values were all high, thus showing that the scale had good internal robustness. The confirmatory factor analyses of the Arabic version of 7-Game Addiction Scale provided further evidence in support of the findings from Lemmens, Valkenburg and Peter (2009). The result is that the single factor model of the 7-item GAS has good psychometric properties and fits the data well in the Saudi adolescent sample.

Game addiction and perceived stress among Saudi adolescents has been investigated by Rajabe and others (2020). As we expected this study demonstrated that game addiction was associated with higher levels of anxiety, depression, and hostility, which contradicts the findings of other studies (Rujataronjai, and Varma, 2017; Brunborg, Mentzoni and Frøyland, 2014; Lemona et al., 2011; Gentile et al., 2011; Mentzoni et al., 2011; Lemmens, Valkenburg and Peter, 2009).

This is the first study, to our knowledge, on video-game addiction among youths using GAS elements as predictors for depression, anxiety, and hostility. The Stepwise method for the prediction of depression showed that mood modification, conflict, and problems were important predictors for the depression score. Furthermore, the multiple regression analyses for the prediction of anxiety showed that mood modification, withdrawal, and salience were important predictors for the anxiety score. In addition, the multiple regression analyses for the prediction of hostility showed that mood modification, tolerance, and conflict were important predictors for the hostility score.

The super-predictor for all subscales of depression, anxiety, and hostility was mood modification. Whereas conflict was a predictor for both depression and hostility.

The predictors for anxiety were withdrawal, for example irritability, tremors, and feeling unpleasant (emotionally and physically), and salience, which means playing games is very important; both of which were predictors for the anxiety score.

In summary, the findings from this study showed that video game addiction is associated with depression, anxiety, and hostility. Furthermore, the study also showed that the game addiction elements (the mood modification, problems, withdrawal, salience, tolerance, and conflict; except relapse) demonstrated significant results as predictors for depression, anxiety, and hostility.

These findings have suggested that more research should be carried out in the future to investigate the role of emotion regulation as a predictor of video game addiction.

Limitations

The results of this study should be interpreted with several limitations in attention. This study dealt with a relatively small sample ($n = 260$) as a result of restriction of Corona virus precautionary measures procedures in high school in Saudi Arabia. <https://iite.unesco.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/The-Saudi-MOE-Leading-Efforts-to-Combat-Coronavirus-Pandemic-COVID-19.pdf>. Recently the procedures of attendance for high school students should be partially attended. (Saudi Ministry of education). <https://english.alarabiya.net/News/gulf/2021/10/20/Saudi-Arabia-postpones-return-of-in-person-learning-for-students-under-age-of-12>

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Author Information

Fahad Saeid Alanazi

Tabuk University

Clinical Psychology Unit
